

VLSI IMPLEMENTATION OF PERFECT SQUARE ROOT CALCULATOR

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ABSTRACT: Square root is a very important mathematical operation which can be used in DSP (Digital Signal Processing)-FPGA (Field Programmable Gate Array) for implementing VLSI signal processing applications. In this paper, an easier method named as repeated subtraction method for finding the perfect square root of a number is discussed. Compared to the Software approach, the FPGA-based approach for finding square roots has several advantages. The VHDL (VHSIC HDL) language is used to design the perfect square root method and the Xilinx Vivado 2015.2 ISE tool is used to implement it on Artix7(7a35t-cpg236) FPGA. Mathematical arithmetic operations on the proposed square root and its VLSI implementation is also discussed in this work. Simulations results captured by the Xilinx Vivado 2015.2 tool verify the correctness of the proposed perfect square root method. Compared with the existing FPGA-based square root method, the proposed square root method is very easy to implement, and it consumes 35LUTs (Look up Tables) and 26FFs (Flip-Flops) at the expense of 20.585W of power.

Keywords: FPGA, VHDL, Perfect Square Root, Repeated Subtraction Method, Xilinx Vivado

I. INTRODUCTION

In applications such as image and audio processing, scientific computation, Spectrum analyzers, computer graphics and digital communications [1, 2, 3, 4] square root is widely used for processing various mathematical operations. Compared with other mathematical operations such as addition, subtraction, multiplication, square root calculation by using hardware is more difficult. Square root computation is more complex than other mathematical operations. It is not easy to get exact result of the hardware implementation of a square root algorithm [5]. The main aim of the FPGA implementation of a square root algorithm is to improve the speed of the computation. Serious care such as operating frequency, area, power consumption and time taken to calculate the square root are considered while implementing square root unit in hardware. Compared with ASICs (Application Specific ICs), FPGA offers several advantages such as flexibility, low power consumption and shorter development time. There are various square root methods such as Long division Method, Prime Factorization, Restoring and Non-restoring Method, Newton-Raphson method [6], Babylonian method [7] and Taylor-Series expansion method [8] can be selected for finding square root of a number in FPGA. Various researchers have used restoring method and non-restoring method to find the square root of a number.

In this paper, an easier method named repeated subtraction method for finding the square root of a number if the number is a perfect square is presented. The proposed method is designed using VHDL and implemented on Artix7 FPGA. Arithmetic operations such as addition, subtraction, multiplication and division operations based on the proposed method are also discussed in this paper. Performance of the proposed square root method in terms of area, power consumption, speed and latency is analyzed and compared with existing square root algorithms.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In the past few years, many square-root computational techniques have been incorporated, namely estimation logic-based Newton-Raphson [9-11], iterative methods [12], Taylor-series expansion

algorithms [13], Cholesky decomposition [14], Sweeney Robertson Toucher-based redundant & non-redundant algorithm [15-19], and non-restoring as well as restoring (digit-by-digit) methodology [20]. Analysis shows that the above-mentioned square root computational algorithm is software-based, which unnecessarily consumes plenty of time to provide final calculations, resulting in delays. However, trending VLSI applications need a technique that has high accuracy in calculation as well as quick processing response and low execution delay (typically should be in nanoseconds). Incorporating the discussed criteria, the Field Programmable Logic Array (FPGA)-based square root calculation technique is nowadays motivating researchers. This technique enhances the computational speed by lowering the execution time (delays). Much research work has been carried out in the last decade to simplify the square root calculation, such as Vedic mathematics, Quake's Algorithm [21-24], non-restoring [27-33], Coordinate Rotation Digital Computer (CORDIC) [28-32], and Piecewise linear (PWL) approximation [33-34]. In [21], Vedic Sutra and Dvand yoga methods were proposed to measure the square root for 16 and 32 bits. The design algorithm utilizes 360 LUTs, 159 flip-flops, and 235 slices at the cost of 98.6 mW power consumption. The blended Vedic method (combination of Indian Vedic and Bakhshali mathematics) has been utilized [22] for square root calculation of 4, 8, and 16-bit. The proposed design requires LUTs of 16, 34 & 103 with power consumption of 2.56, 3.15 & 3.96 mW respectively for 4, 8, & 16-bit. In [23], an 8-bit radicand-based Vedic square root calculator has been discussed at the cost of 26 LUTs and 12.879ns latency. Abdul Hasnat et al. proposed Quake's algorithm for square root computation [24]. The designed system requires 12 clock cycles to produce a final result at 1194.122 MHz frequency. The non-restoring square root algorithm has been designed and implemented on the FPGA in [24], [25], [26]. The design structure utilizes subtract operation and spends 01 while neglecting to add an operator and append 11 to make hardware efficient. Imtiaz Sajid et al. has proposed a modified pipelined architecture for N-bit square root operation [27]. The designed mechanism not only has 13% better latency, but has improved speed (4 times higher than other counterparts). Research in [28] reports four multiplier-based square root calculators. The design stops processing once it achieves the final calculation, resulting in a reduction in iteration. To eliminate the separate requirement for hardware, decrease power consumption, and reduce the chip area, the CORDIC square algorithm has been discussed [28-32]. The reported CORDIC square root computation in [28] and [29] utilizes the UMC of a 90-nm technology node with 1.08V at 1 MHz and the UMC of a 180-nm technology node with 1.0V at 5 MHz, respectively. However, in [30], TSMC of 45-nm CMOS technology at 1 GHz frequency is used. Apart from having all such advantages, CORDIC methodology suffers with high latency during multiple iterations. Moreover, PWL approximation helps to encounter the latency issue of CORDIC methodology [36-37]. Fei Lyu et al. reported a PWL square root algorithm with TSMC of 40-nm CMOS for Nth root [36]. Furthermore, Yu Wang et al. proposed a mechanism having TSMC of 65-nm CMOS for complex square roots [37].

III. PROPOSED SQUARE ROOT METHOD

The square root of any number is a value and if the number is multiplied by itself, it gives the original number. In this work, the square root of an unsigned binary number using a repeated subtraction method is designed using VHDL.

3.1 Repeated Subtraction Method

If a number is perfect square, then we can determine its square root by the repeated subtraction method by following the below steps:

- From the original unsigned binary number, continuously subtract consecutive odd numbers (starting from 1) from it.
- This subtraction continues until the difference between a number and an odd number reaches equal to a zero value.
- The Square root of the original number is the count value of number of subtraction steps.

Below are examples of finding a square root by repeated subtraction method:

1. If the original number is 25, and you want to find square root of this number by repeated subtraction method, than you have to follow below steps:

- 25 -1 = 24 1st Subtraction step, Count Value=1
- 24-3 = 21 2nd Subtraction step, Count Value=2
- 21-5= 16 3rd Subtraction step, Count Value=3
- 16-7= 9 4th Subtraction step, Count Value=4
- 9-9 = 0 5th Subtraction step, Count Value=5

Since in the 5th subtraction step, subtraction value is zero, so the count value is 5 and the square root of perfect number 25 is 5.

2. If the original number is 400 and you want to find square root of this number by repeated subtraction method, than you have to follow the below steps:

- 400 -1 =399 1st Subtraction step, Count Value=1
- 399- 3 = 396 2nd Subtraction step, Count Value=2
- 396 -5= 391 3rd Subtraction step, Count Value=3
- 391-7= 384 4th Subtraction step, Count Value=4
- 384-9 = 375 5th Subtraction step, Count Value=5
- 375-11 =364 6th Subtraction step, Count Value=6
- 364-13 = 351 7th Subtraction step, Count Value=7
- 351-15=336 8th Subtraction step, Count Value=8
- 336-17=319 9th Subtraction step, Count Value=9
- 319-19=300 10th Subtraction step, Count Value=10
- 300-21=279 11th Subtraction step, Count Value=11
- 279-23= 256 12th Subtraction step, Count Value=12
- 256-25=231 13th Subtraction step, Count Value=13
- 231-27=204 14th Subtraction step, Count Value=14
- 204-29=175 15th Subtraction step, Count Value=15
- 175-31=144 16th Subtraction step, Count Value=16
- 144-33= 111 17th Subtraction step, Count Value=17
- 111-35= 76 18th Subtraction step, Count Value=18
- 76- 37 =39 19th Subtraction step, Count Value=19
- 39 - 39 = 0 20th Subtraction step, Count Value=20

In the 20th subtraction step, subtraction value is a zero value, hence the 20th subtraction step count value is the square root value of the original number 400.Hence, square root of perfect number 400 is 20.

In this method, an integer counter starting form one, and it adds two to the count value for every rising edge of clock is designed using VHDL .And this counter stops counting when the subtraction step value reaches a zero value. The count value of this counter is as follows:1,3,5,7,9,11,13,15,17.....For finding square root of the original number, another integer counter for counting number of valid subtraction steps is designed using VHDL. The initial value of this counter is one and it adds one on the count value for the every rising edge of clock. This counter stops counting when subtraction step value reaches a zero value. Count value of this counter is as follows:1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16.....

3.2 Mathematical Operations on Square Root

In this work, mathematical operations such as addition, subtraction, multiplication and division with a scalar value are computed on the proposed square root method. If k1 and K2 are two scalar values and a and b are perfect numbers, then we can perform the following mathematical operations:

- $K1\sqrt{a} + k2\sqrt{b}$
- $K1\sqrt{a} - k2\sqrt{b}$
- $\frac{k1\sqrt{a}}{k2\sqrt{b}}$
- $K1\sqrt{a} \times k2\sqrt{b}$

All these operations are performed using VHDL.

Figure.3: The Simulation output waveform for Arithmetic operation performed on square root. In Fig.3, signal x1 and x2 are two 9bit unsigned binary perfect numbers, signal k1 and k2 are two scalar values, signal sel is 3bit input number for selecting a particular mathematical operations on square roots, and signal arithop is an output value for the particular mathematical operations on performed on square roots of input perfect number x1 and x2. In this figure, if sel value is “000” then, mathematical addition operation is performed with k1 and k2 value one, if sel value is “001” then, mathematical subtraction operation is performed with k1 and k2 value one, if sel value is “010” then, mathematical multiplication operation is performed with k1 and k2 value one, if sel value is “011” then, mathematical division operation is performed with k1 and k2 value one, if sel value is “100” then, mathematical addition operation is performed with k1 and k2 value two and if sel value is “101” then, mathematical subtraction operation is performed with k1 and k2 value two. RTL schematic diagram for the arithmetic operations performed on the proposed square root method is shown in Figure.4.

Figure.4: RTL diagram for the Arithmetic operation performed on the proposed square root method. Synthesis results for the Arithmetic operation performed on the proposed square root method are shown in Table. II.

Table. II: Synthesis results for the Arithmetic operation performed on the proposed square root method

	Area(LUTs/FFs) and DSP48	Speed(ns)	Total on Chip Power Consumption(Watt)
Arithmetic operation performed proposed Repeated Square Root Method	1614/40, 9	106.293	47.611

Arithmetic operation performed on the proposed square root system consume 1614 LUTs, 40FFs and consume 47.611W of power. It consumes 9 DSP48 blocks. DSP48 blocks in Artix7 FPGA are used for addition, multiplication, and accumulation operations. Performance comparison among square root calculator systems are shown in Table .III. Compared to Paper [9, 10, 11, 12], the proposed square root calculator consume fewer LUTs and FFs. Also, it operates at higher speed in comparison with existing square root calculator systems. Proposed square root calculator system has a low latency computation value in comparison with Paper [9] at the expense of more power consumption.

Table. III: Performance comparison among various square root calculator systems

Square root calculator system	Area	Speed(ns)	Total on Chip Power Consumption(Watt)	Latency (clock cycles)	Device
Proposed Square Root System based on repeated subtraction method	35LUTs and 26 FFs	6.139	20.585	1	Artix7
[30] Radicand width (8 bit) area optimized	39 Logic Elements and 27 FFs	22.9	0.0852	4	Altera DE2
[30] Radicand width (16 bit) area optimized	78 Logic Elements and 48 FFs	90.1	0.0866	8	Altera DE2
[30] Radicand width (32 bit) area optimized	123 Logic Elements and 89 FFs	144.4	0.0891	16	Altera DE2
[38]	577 LUTS and 420FFs	66	0.141		Xilinx Zynq-7000
[39]	817 LUTs and 333FFs	92.4	0.303		Altera Stratix-II
[40]	173 LUTs and 99 FFs	14.66	0.0909		SPARTAN-3E

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, a hardware implementation of a square root calculator system based on the repeated subtraction method is presented. The proposed square root calculator system consumes low area, it has a low latency computation value, and it operates at higher speed. Correctness of the proposed square root calculator system is obtained from simulation results captured by Xilinx Vivado 2015.2 ISE tool and hardware verification is done by using Artix7 FPGA. The proposed square root calculator system consumes 20.585 W of power, and consumes 35LUTs and 26FFs. It operates at a maximum frequency of value 61.96MHz (6.139ns). RTL schematic diagrams for the proposed square root calculator system and for its arithmetic operations are shown in this paper. Arithmetic operations on the proposed square root calculator system are also presented in this paper. The proposed square root calculator system can be easily extended for higher number of input bits. This system can be used for real-time arithmetic calculations based on square roots.

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